

A Comparative Analysis Of Domestic Violence Between Pakistan And India

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Honorable Editor

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Regards,

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Abstract

This comparative analysis digs into domestic violence in Pakistan and India, inspecting its prevalence, causes, and consequences. Established in male-centric standards and orientation imbalance, domestic violence appears in different structures — physical, profound, and sexual maltreatment. Social standards, monetary incongruities, and restricted asset access propagate its propagation. Notwithstanding existing legal frameworks, execution challenges persevere, featuring the requirement for exhaustive measures, including legal reforms, education, and cultural changes. The review highlights the effect on people, families, and society, accentuating the pattern of violence and the transmission of conduct across ages. It focuses on the significance of mindfulness, support administrations, and orientation equity advancement to really battle domestic violence. The analysis calls for earnest activity to guarantee the security and prosperity of people and families in both countries through cooperative endeavors across legal, instructive, and cultural domains.

Keywords: cultural factors, legal framework, gender dynamics, intervention programs, educational initiatives, prevalence

Introduction

Domestic violence is a far reaching issue that influences people, families, social orders around the world. This comparative analysis means to reveal insight into the pervasiveness and nature of domestic violence in two adjoining nations, Pakistan and India. By analyzing the similitudes and contrasts in the unique situation, causes, and consequences of domestic violence in these nations, we can acquire a more profound comprehension of this perplexing social issue. Both countries share similar cultural and social elements, yet striking contrasts exist in their separate social orders, prevalence, basic elements, and reactions to domestic violence. (Karmaliani et al., 2019; Ragavan et al., 2018).

Domestic violence, defined as the pattern of abusive behaviors by one partner against another in an intimate relationship, is a pervasive problem in both Pakistan and India (Goel & Goktepe-Hulten, 2018; Sadiq et al., 2017). However, the manifestations and extent of domestic violence differ between the two countries. This analysis will examine the cultural, legal, and social frameworks that shape the attitudes towards domestic violence, as well as the impact of these factors on victims and their access to support services (Jain, 2018; Krishnan et al., 2020).

By fundamentally contrasting the pervasiveness and types of domestic violence in Pakistan and India, we expect to reveal insight into the extraordinary difficulties and open doors for resolving this issue within each country (Das, 2019; Giri et al., 2017). Besides, we will investigate the current regulations, arrangements, and cultural mentalities that prevent or facilitate efforts to battle domestic violence to distinguish

compelling methodologies for counteraction and intercession (Tahir et al., 2018; Sardinha et al., 2019).

Eventually, this comparative analysis looks to add to a more profound comprehension of domestic violence in Pakistan and India, giving experiences that can illuminate designated interventions, policy reforms, and promotion endeavors to cultivate more secure and more steady conditions for people impacted by domestic violence in both nations (Jeyaseelan et al., 2015)

Research Justification

Domestic violence stays a critical social issue with significant suggestions for people, families, and communities. In spite of extensive examination and intervention efforts, there is a remarkable gap in comparative analysis, especially between nations like Pakistan and India. These two countries share verifiable, cultural, and social similitudes, yet their ways to deal with tending to domestic violence may contrast because of fluctuating legal frameworks, cultural norms, and socioeconomic factors. By directing a comparative analysis, this exploration expects to reveal insight into the similarities, differences, and fundamental elements adding to domestic violence in Pakistan and India. Such insights of knowledge are important for policymakers, activists, and practitioners to foster more successful systems for preventions and intervention.

Research Objectives

1: To examine the legal frameworks and strategy responses tending to domestic violence in Pakistan and India, that includes the viability of legislation, law implementation and support services.

2: To examine the effect of domestic violence on people, families, and communities in the both nations, including physical and psychological well-being outcomes, inter-generational transmission, and social attachment.

3: To recognize best practices and examples gained from both country's methodologies to addressing to domestic violence, to inform policy suggestions and intervention for the two countries and beyond.

Research Methodology

This research was formed by a systematic review method. The research objectives are determined by this method, and an extensive literature review is conducted on the subject. The research findings are classified according to the subject's content (Hiver et al., 2021; Petticrew & Roberts, 2006). Classified information is included in the study by organizing it as headings (Pawson et al., 2005). The study flow is formed by evaluating classified information and titles (Rahi, 2017). Thus, integrity is ensured by evaluating the researched subject's content (Eggers & Steinert, 2022; Victor et al., 2018) Consequently, this technique was selected, and the associated processes were observed. Reviewing the relevant literature resulted in accumulating data and information coded according to the study goals. The coded data were grouped by subject. After classifying and merging the subjects, they were ordered by degree of connection.

Literature Review

Domestic violence is an inescapable issue influencing people and families around the world, with huge ramifications for general wellbeing and social prosperity. In the

context of South Asia, countries like India and Pakistan wrestle with the multi-layered challenges presented by domestic violence, which are molded by cultural, socioeconomic and legal elements.

- 1. prevalence and patterns of domestic violence:** Studies have reliably shown high paces of domestic violence in both India and Pakistan. Research by Kishor and Johnson, (2004) found that almost 33% of married ladies in India revealed encountering physical or sexual violence from their life partners. Additionally, concentrates in Pakistan, for example, the Pakistan Demographic and Health Survey (PDHS) led in 2017-18, uncovered alarmingly high rates of intimate partner violence against women.
- 2. Sociocultural factors:** Gender inequality, settled in male centric norms, and rigid gender roles contribute fundamentally to the perpetuation of domestic violence in both countries. In India, traditional thoughts of manliness and family honor frequently legitimize oppressive ways of behaving towards women (National Crime Records Bureau, 2019). Also, in Pakistan, cultural norms directing women's subordinate status and dutifulness to male authority act as hidden factors fueling domestic violence (Jafri, 2015).
- 3. Legal frameworks and policy responses:** Both India and Pakistan implemented laws aimed at addressing domestic violence. India's protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA) was enacted in 2005 to provide legal protections and support services for survivors, while Pakistan responded with the Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Act passed in 2012. The successful enforcement of these regulations in both nations faces challenges due to execution hurdles, lack of

awareness, and inadequate resources. (Das, 2019; Karmaliani et al., 2017).

- 4. Impact on health and well-being:** Domestic violence has significant consequences for the physical, mental, and emotional health of survivors. Studies have reported the connection between domestic violence and unfriendly wellbeing results, including wounds, chronic medical issue, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Ali et al., 2020; Sudha et al., 2015). Additionally, intergenerational violence propagates patterns of misuse and sabotages social union inside communities.
- 5. Challenges and opportunities for intervention:** While huge difficulties continue tending to domestic violence in India and Pakistan, there are too amazing open doors for intervention and progress. community-based initiative, advocacy campaigns, and associations between government organizations and civil society associations are critical in bringing issues to light, offering support services, and upholding for policy reforms (Kalra et al., 2018; Saleem & Agarwal, 2021). At last, the comparative analysis of domestic violence in India and Pakistan highlights the mind boggling exchange of sociocultural, legal, and structural factors molding the predominance, experiences, and responses to intimate partner violence. By understanding these elements and recognizing compelling techniques, policymakers, practitioners, and advocates can make progress toward making more secure and more fair social orders for all people.
- 6. Comparative Analysis of Case Studies:** An instance of domestic violence in Pakistan was the homicide of virtual entertainment star Qandeel Baloch in 2016 by her sibling. Baloch, known for her provocative online posts, was choked to death in what her sibling asserted was an "honor killing" for carrying shame to the

family. This case ignited public and global shock, revealing insight into the prevalence of honor killings and domestic violence in Pakistan. An instance of domestic violence in India is the 2012 Nirbhaya case. A young lady, alluded to as Nirbhaya to safeguard her character, was ruthlessly gang-raped and tortured on a transport in Delhi by six men, including an adolescent. The occurrence prompted inescapable fights across India, demanding equity for Nirbhaya and featuring the issue of violence against women in the country. The case focused on the commonness of domestic violence and the pressing need for more grounded laws and cultural changes to shield women from such outrages.

Laws Related to Domestic Violence in India

1. Indian Penal Code, 1860.
2. Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961.
3. Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005.
4. The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013.

Laws Related to Domestic Violence in Pakistan

1. Protection of Women (Criminal Laws Amendment) Act, 2006.
2. Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Act, 2012.
3. The Sindh Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Act, 2013.
4. The Punjab Protection of Women against Violence Act, 2016.

Similarities in Domestic Violence between Pakistan and India

- 1. Prevalence of Domestic Violence:** Domestic violence is an unavoidable issue in both countries, cutting across socioeconomic, religious, and cultural lines. Women from all backgrounds experience different types of abuse inside their families.
- 2. Legal Frameworks:** The two India and Pakistan have enacted legislation to address domestic violence and give legal protections to survivors. In any case, enforcement and execution fluctuate, with gaps existing in the two countries

Differences in Domestic Violence between Pakistan and India

- 1. Legal Landscape:** While the two countries have laws tending to domestic violence, the specific legal arrangements and mechanisms differ. For instance, India has the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act of 2005, while Pakistan enacted the Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Act of 2012.
- 2. Cultural Context:** Cultural nuances and practices encompassing marriage, dowry, and family structures vary among India and Pakistan, affecting the elements of domestic violence in every country. While India and Pakistan share common challenges connected with domestic violence coming from male centric norms and cultural mentalities, contrasts in legal frameworks, and cultural contexts, understanding these subtleties is fundamental for tailored interventions and policy initiatives pointed toward addressing to domestic violence successfully in both contexts.

Discussion

This comparative analysis digs into the perplexing issue of domestic violence in Pakistan and India, revealing insight into its predominance, causes, and consequences in

both countries. Established in profoundly imbued male centric norms and gender imbalances, domestic violence appears in different structures, including physical, emotional, and sexual misuse. Cultural norms, economic disparities, and restricted admittance to education and resources contribute to its persistence.

The review looks at the current legal frameworks and emotionally supportive system to battle domestic violence in the two countries, surveying their viability and highlighting execution challenges. It underscores the critical requirement for thorough measures, including legal reforms, education, and cultural changes, to address this inescapable issue.

Besides, the analysis highlights the impact of domestic violence on people, families, and society all in all, underlining the pattern of violence and the transmission of harmful ways of behaving across generations. It focuses on the significance of bringing issues to light, offering support services, and elevating gender equality to successfully battle domestic violence in Pakistan and India, guaranteeing the wellbeing and prosperity of all people and families.

Conclusion

The comparative analysis of domestic violence in India and Pakistan uncovers the two shared characteristics and unmistakable difficulties inside the context of South Asian social orders. While the two countries share male centric norms, gender imbalances, and legal frameworks pointed toward tending to domestic violence, nuances in cultural practices, socioeconomic dynamics, and regional disparities shape the manifestation and reaction to this pervasive issue. despite efforts to enact legislation and give legal protections to survivors, critical gaps exist in the implementations and

enforcement of domestic violence laws in the two countries. Bureaucratic inefficiencies, corruption, and absence of awareness among law enforcement agencies ruin access to justice for survivors, especially in marginalized communities.

The impact of conflict and political instability further convolutes efforts to address domestic violence, with regions impacted by conflict experiences heightened levels of violence against women and restricted access to support services. Militarization, displacements, and breakdown of social structures intensify existing vulnerabilities, highlighting the requirement for tailored interventions in conflict-affected areas.

Societal perspectives and disgrace surrounding domestic violence propagate silence and frustrate help-seeking ways of behaving among survivors. Cultural norms, religious beliefs, and gender philosophies shape perceptions of domestic violence, requiring coordinated efforts to challenge winning perspectives and cultivate a culture of zero capacity to bear violence against women. Inter-sectional dimension of domestic violence, including race, ethnicity, religion, disability, and sexual orientations, highlight the need for designated interventions that address the particular requirements and difficulties looked by marginalized groups.

Considering these intricacies, stakeholders should embrace all-encompassing approaches that address structural inequalities, promote gender equality, and give complete support services for survivors. By cross examining societal norms, legal frameworks, and inter-sectional dynamics, policymakers, advocates, and communities can pursue making more secure and more comprehensive social orders where all people can reside free from the scourge of domestic violence.

Recommendations

1. Explore the historical factors that have influenced attitudes towards domestic violence in India and Pakistan.
2. Compare the laws and policies related to domestic violence in both countries.
3. Examine how cultural beliefs and practices contribute to the prevalence of domestic violence in India and Pakistan.
4. Analyze the impact of traditional gender roles on domestic violence in both societies.
5. Compare the effectiveness of reporting mechanisms and support services for domestic violence survivors in India and Pakistan.
6. Investigate how socioeconomic disparities contribute to domestic violence in both countries.
7. Assess the role of education and awareness campaigns in addressing domestic violence in India and Pakistan.
8. Explore the influence of religion on attitudes towards domestic violence in both countries.
9. Examine how the prevalence and perception of domestic violence vary between urban and rural areas in India and Pakistan.
10. Investigate the impact of domestic violence on children and the availability of support services for them in both countries.
11. Analyze how the media portrays domestic violence and its impact on public perception and awareness in India and Pakistan.

12. Compare the government initiatives and policies aimed at preventing and addressing domestic violence in India and Pakistan.
13. Evaluate the role of non-governmental organizations in providing support to domestic violence survivors in both countries.
14. Explore how stigma and shame surrounding domestic violence affect reporting and seeking help in India and Pakistan.
15. Consider how domestic violence in India and Pakistan compares to other countries in the region or globally, and identify potential lessons that can be learned from these comparisons.

Research Limitations

Comparative analysis of domestic violence in India and Pakistan is the challenge of getting predictable and solid information across the two countries. Each country has its own legal and social frameworks, which might vary as far as defining, reporting, and addressing to domestic violence. Varieties in cultural norms, religious beliefs, and socioeconomic factors can likewise impact how domestic violence is perceived, reported, and addressed to in every country.

Contrasts in research methodologies, examining strategies, and information assortment tools can additionally muddle the comparison. For example, the meaning of domestic violence might change between studies, prompting irregularities in the information. Also, cultural sensitivities and bias intrinsic in surveys or interviews might impact the reactions got from participants, possibly slanting the outcomes. Another constraint is the absence of longitudinal examinations that track changes in domestic violence patterns over the long run in the two India and Pakistan. Longitudinal

information could give important experiences into the adequacy of interventions, policy changes, and socioeconomic advancements in tending to domestic violence.

A comparative analysis requires a nuanced understanding of both countries' historical, political, and sociocultural contexts. Overlooking these intricacies may distort the examination and lead to mistaken ends. Given the sensitive nature of domestic violence, there might be moral contemplations and challenges in guaranteeing the wellbeing and privacy of participant, especially in regions where it is no or unsafe to report or examining such issues. It requires cautious thought of strategic methodologies, cross-cultural sensitivity, and collaborations with neighborhood stakeholders to assemble thorough and exact information on domestic violence in India and Pakistan.

Research Implications

Comparative analysis of domestic violence in India and Pakistan has the potential to distinguish normal fundamental factors adding to this issue across different cultural and socioeconomic contexts. By analyzing similarities and differences in prevalence, patterns, and reactions to domestic violence, policymakers and practitioners can foster more designated and successful interventions tailored to the particular requirements of every country.

Such research could feature regions for cross-border collaborations effort and information trade, working with the sharing of best practices and resources to address domestic violence more extensively in South Asia. It could prompt the advancement of regional strategies and associations pointed toward battling domestic violence and advancing gender equality across borders.

Future Research Directions

Comparative analysis of domestic violence in India and Pakistan could include investigating the impact of advancing socioeconomic elements, like urbanization, globalization, and technological advancement, on patterns of domestic violence in the two countries. Investigating how changing societal structure and gender roles cross with conventional cultural norms and legal frameworks could give important insights into arising trends and challenges in pointing to domestic violence.

There is a requirement for longitudinal studies that track the effectiveness of interventions and policy initiatives aimed at forestalling and lessening domestic violence over the long haul. Understanding the long term outcomes of different intervention techniques, including legal reforms, community based programs, and educational campaign, can inform evidence based approaches for handling domestic violence in diverse contexts inside India and Pakistan.

Future research could dive into the intersectionality of domestic violence with different types of mistreatment, for example, caste based discrimination, religious persecution, and financial disparity, to better understand how marginalization contributes to vulnerability and barriers to seeking for help among impacted people. Investigating the role of advanced technologies, social media, and online platforms in both sustaining and battling domestic violence warrants considerations. Investigating how technology intervened communication and support networks impact the elements of domestic violence and access to resources for survivors could inform innovative strategies for prevention and intervention in the digital age.

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